

Plant High Molecular Weight (HMW) DNA Manual Extraction Protocol

Version 2, updated March 2025

What is needed

Reagents:

- Sorbitol wash solution from Jones and Schwessinger, 2020, with final concentrations of:
 - 0.35 M D-Sorbitol
 - 1% w/v PVP-40
 - 0.1 M Tris-HCl pH 8.0
 - 5 mM EDTA pH 8.0
- Lysis Buffer adapted from Schalamun et al, 2018, with final concentrations of:
 - 1% w/v PVP-40
 - 1% w/v Sodium metabisulfite
 - 0.5 M Sodium Chloride
 - 0.1 M Tris-HCl pH 8.0
 - 0.05 mM EDTA, pH 8.0
 - 1.5% w/v Sodium dodecyl sulphate (SDS)
- 1,4-Dithiothreitol (DTT)
- 20 mg/mL Proteinase K
- 20 mg/mL RNase A
- 1% β -Mercaptoethanol (BME)
- 5M Potassium acetate
- 100% Chloroform cooled to -20°C
- 100% Isopropyl alcohol cooled to -20°C
- 70% Ethanol cooled to -20°C
- Nuclease free dH₂O
- Qubit reagent

Equipment:

- Pipettes (P1000, P200, P20, P10)
- Centrifuge to spin 50 mL tubes @ 5000 g
- Centrifuge to spin 2 mL tubes @ 5000 g
- Fume hood
- Water bath
- Rotating tube mixer
- 50 mL Nalgene centrifuge tube (reusable, autoclaved)
- Mortar and pestle (autoclaved)
- Spatula and scissors (autoclaved)
- Polystyrene ice box
- Nanodrop
- Qubit

Consumables:

- 2 mL DNA LoBind Eppendorf tubes
- 1.5 mL DNA LoBind Eppendorf tubes
- 50 mL conical tubes

- P1000 wide bore tips
- P200 wide bore tips
- P1000 tips
- P200/P20 tips
- P10 tips
- Liquid nitrogen
- Qubit tubes

Personal protective equipment (PPE):

- Closed shoes
- Safety goggles
- Thermal gloves

Protocol to extract HMW DNA from a single plant sample**Sampling:**

1. Cut plant leaf material into a pre-cooled mortar filled with liquid nitrogen. Ensure the necessary PPE is worn.
2. Pulverize 3 g of plant tissue in liquid nitrogen. Grind for at least 25 min until leaf material is a smooth, homogenous fine powder. Transfer the tissue to a pre-cooled 50mL Nalgene extraction tube using a pre-cooled spatula. Store the extraction tube in the liquid nitrogen until the sorbitol wash is added.

Sorbitol wash:

3. Prepare the sorbitol wash solution beforehand:
Prepare ~150 mL sorbitol wash per 3 g tissue prepared for extraction. Add 3x small scoops of DTT to 50 mL of the sorbitol wash in a 50 mL Falcon tube solution just before use (work in a fume hood).
4. Resuspend 3 g of ground tissue in 25 mL sorbitol wash solution in the 50 mL Nalgene tube. Make sure the tissue is homogenised in the sorbitol solution by shaking vigorously. Make sure all the tissue is in solution without any lumps.
5. Centrifuge at 5000 g, room temperature for 8 min (if working with a plant that has a loose pellet, the time can be adjusted to prevent loss of tissue).
6. Pour off the supernatant and repeat steps 5-6 until supernatant is clear (minimum of 6X).
7. During the final sorbitol wash, resuspend the tissue in exactly 15 mL of sorbitol wash solution. Once tissue is homogenous in solution, transfer 1.5 mL of homogenous tissue + sorbitol solution to a 2 mL DNA LoBind Eppendorf tube (total of 10X 2 mL tubes per 3 g tissue) using a P1000 pipette and wide bore pipette tip.
8. Centrifuge at 5000 g, room temperature for 5 min.
9. Pour off the supernatant.

Cell lysis:

10. Pre-mix Lysis buffer, Proteinase K and RNase A for 10X 2 mL Eppendorf tubes:
10 ml Lysis buffer, 50 μ L Proteinase K (20 mg/mL) and 20 μ L RNase A (20 mg/ml) in a 50 mL Falcon tube.
11. Add 800 μ L of the pre-mixed Lysis buffer to each 2 mL Eppendorf tube. Mix gently using a P1000 pipette and a wide bore tip by pulsating the pipette 2X and gently flicking the tube until the pellet is dissolved and solution is homogenous.
12. Incubate at 37°C for 30 minutes (can to use lukewarm water).
13. Add 8 μ L of 1% BME to each tube (work in a fume hood) and invert tubes 3X. Ensure that everything is in solution.

14. Incubate at 65°C in a water bath for 10 minutes. Mix every 2 minutes by gentle inversion.
15. Remove samples from water bath and gently invert tubes 3X to get everything into solution.
16. Place samples on ice for 4 minutes to cool down.
17. Add 150 uL Potassium acetate to each tube, invert tubes 3X and place back on ice for 20 minutes (work in a fume hood).

DNA purification and precipitation:

18. Add 500 uL chloroform previously cooled to -20°C to each tube (work in a fume hood).
19. Shake well to get everything homogenous and place on rotating tube mixer with 360° rotation at room temperature for 10 min.
20. Centrifuge for 10 min @1300 g, room temperature.
21. Transfer 700 uL of the aqueous phase using a P200 pipette, wide bore pipette tips and slow pipetting to a new 1.5 mL DNA LoBind Eppendorf tube (work in a fume hood).
22. If aqueous phase appears very murky after centrifugation step, add 150 uL Potassium acetate to each tube.
23. Repeat steps 18 to 21 (can work on the bench for the repeats).
24. Add an equal volume (700 uL) of isopropyl alcohol previously cooled to -20°C. Mix gently by slowly inverting tubes 5X. Place the samples at -20°C. for 1h.

Washing and resuspension:

25. Centrifuge for 5 min at 4000 g, room temperature (place Eppendorf tubes with the back of tube facing to the back of the rotor to help locate pellet). Discard the supernatant carefully. Be careful not to lose your pellet; some may be transparent and stuck to the side of the tube.
26. Resuspend the pellet in 1 mL of 70% ethanol previously cooled to -20°C. Mix gently by flicking and inverting tubes 5X. Make sure the pellet dislodges from the bottom.
27. Centrifuge for 5 min at 4000 g, room temperature (place Eppendorf tubes with back of tube facing to the back of the rotor to help locate pellet). Discard the supernatant gently.
28. Repeat steps 26 and 27.
29. After a quick spin down, immediately take off excess ethanol using a P10 pipette without touching the pellet. Allow to dry for maximum 30 seconds.
30. Resuspend the pellet in 13 -23 µL (depending on the size of the pellet) nuclease free dH₂O. Ensure that the pellet is fully dislodged from the bottom of the tube.
31. Store at 4°C overnight before proceeding to the quality control steps. DO NOT FREEZE HMW DNA!

Quality control:

32. Allow samples to come to room temperature. Flick each tube gently to ensure the pellet is in solution. If the solution is gel-like or the pellet is not yet in solution, use a wide bore tip and gently pipette up and down to dissolve it. Add more dH₂O if needed. DO NOT VORTEX HMW DNA!
33. Nanodrop and Qubit all samples.
34. Pool the samples into one tube using a wide bore tip. Do not pool samples that are outliers based on the nanodrop ratios and Qubit concentrations.
35. Qubit and nanodrop the final sample again.
36. Send DNA for fragment length analysis.

